

CASE STUDY OF ANTI-CANAL ACTIVISM ON THE INDUS RIVER IN SINDH: A CONTENT ANALYSIS OF PROTEST LANGUAGE THROUGH DIGITAL LINGUISTIC LANDSCAPE

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Abstract

This study examines the performative aspects of protest and language tactics employed by Sindhi speakers in Sindh, Pakistan, who are against the Indus River Canal Project. The research uses a qualitative case study technique and the Digital Linguistic Landscape (DLL) framework to evaluate protest related information from digital platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp, and online news websites. The dataset comprised social media postings, protest photographs, newspaper articles, chants, music, poetry, graffiti, and AI-generated visuals. Purposive sampling was used to collect materials that were relevant to protest narratives. The data were evaluated using qualitative content analysis, with a focus on the contextual and communicative functions of language in protest language. The study also uses Tilly's (2004) WUNC framework (Worthiness, Unity, Numbers, and Commitment) to evaluate how protestors approached their right to protest. Linguistic analysis, including vocabulary choices, grammatical structures, and discourse techniques, was also conducted. To maintain ethical considerations, only publicly posted visual data was analyzed. The findings shed light on the interplay of language, internet activism, and united resistance in a regional environmental justice movement.

INTRODUCTION

Protests are a political form of expression and an act of resistance exercised by groups and communities who face inconvenience, injustice, or oppression. The purpose of a protest is not just to gather a group of people to voice their concerns but to “influence a change in a particular situation.” (Iyoha, 2023). Protests are a salient feature of democratic societies as protests have influenced, created, and significantly contributed to building popular democracies in the world (van Dijk, 1998).

Protests as political tools of expression have been globally used to raise a voice against issues such as social, political, religious, gender, and climate

injustice, as well as to speak out against the misuse of power by influential people and wealthy organizations. People often resort to protests when other methods of communication, such as dialogue and negotiations with authorities, prove unsuccessful. Just as the reasons to protest are varied, so are the ways to protest. Depending on the urgency and the severity of the matter, the protests may range from peaceful marches and sit-ins to strikes, boycotts, and civil disobedience. Moreover, with the advent of social media, hashtags and digital content also serve as a means to aid the protest movements, such is the case with anti-canal protests happening in Sindh, Pakistan.

Presently, Pakistan is seeing protests in most major cities of Sindh against the proposed Cholistan Canal, one of the key components of the Green Pakistan Initiative (GPI). In 2025, a project was launched under the Green Pakistan Initiative to irrigate barren land in Punjab's Cholistan area by drawing new canals from the Indus River. This project has met with serious reservations from Pakistan People's Party (PPP) and the people of Sindh, as the Indus River is the source of Sindh's agriculture, fisheries, and other forms of livelihood, along with being Sindh's major source of water supply (Dawn, 2025).

Cholistan Desert is one of the largest deserts of Pakistan, which is facing issues such as extreme scarcity of water, drought, overgrazing, deforestation, wind erosion, salinity, and encroachment for expanding agriculture that results in the decline of natural resources (Qureshi et al., 2024). This contentious project has sparked heated debates not just over the fair distribution of Pakistan's limited water resources but also over "the underlying logic of its water sourcing strategy, the reliability of engineering assumptions, and the long-term implications for interprovincial equity" (Nazar, 2025).

Research Objectives

- To analyse the linguistic framing strategies used by protestors in opposition to the canal on the Indus River in Sindh.
- To analyze how protestors display worthiness, unity, numbers, and commitment (WUNC) during the protest movement.

Research Questions:

1. How do protestors frame their opposition to the canal through language?
2. How do protestors in the Indus Canal Project demonstrate worthiness, unity, numbers, and commitment?

Literature Review:

Protest studies have employed different research methodologies over the decades, but the one that remains popular is Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA). One reason why CDA is a popular framework to study socio-political events, such as protests, could be due to its underlying theory which states that the injustices of society resulting from the uneven power

distribution can be "enacted, (re)produced, legitimated and resisted by text and talk in a social and political context" (Van Dijk, 2015).

Ming and Wang (2022) conducted a study using CDA to examine the discursive strategies employed by protesters in social media and traditional media's representations of Hong Kong's protests against the proposed extradition bill in 2019–20. The study concluded that different media outlets portrayed protests in different lights depending on "the different roles and functions of the two newspapers in their respective sociopolitical contexts". Moreover, in Sydney, Catanzaro & Collin (2023) conducted a study analyzing the placards created by students of different ages during the largest climate change advocacy rally held in September 2019. This study found that visual communication, such as through placards, signs, and posters, plays a crucial role in expressing and leveraging the emotional responses of the masses towards social issues.

Likewise, in Pakistan's research context, protest studies primarily employ the CDA framework for data analysis. One such study was conducted by Akhtar et al. (2021), which explored the sentiments shared by Pakistani women regarding their gender-based struggles at Aurat March 2019 through protest signs, slogans, messages, and banners. Similarly, CDA framework was employed to analyze the political slogans of major political parties in Pakistan's 2018 election (Kaleem et al., 2022), how power dynamics are exercised in Pakistani political discourse through analysis of PMLN leader Nawaz Sharif's speeches (Waqar & Khan, 2025), and how political slogans shape national identity in Pakistan (Nawaz et al., 2024). Using social media as the field of research, Siddiqua et al. (2023) explored how 4 female Pakistani journalists were harassed online through qualitative analysis of 239 tweets.

However, CDA has recently been identified as a method lacking accountability in terms of its qualitative analysis approach. As a result, new approaches have been introduced in the study of protests and how they are represented in traditional media and social media platforms. Tilly's sociological Worthiness, Unity, Numbers, and Commitment (WUNC) framework is an example of one such new method that promises to enhance CDA theories and create a more holistic analysis method for studying

protest language. Kennedy (2022) applied the WUNC methodology to analyze the data of 76 articles reporting pro- and anti- Brexit protests.

Corpus-based approach is also becoming popular because a large amount of online data is available, which reveals key insights into the mind and the sentiments of protesters, as demonstrated by Hansson, et al, (2022). The researchers in this study used a corpus-based approach to collect data from X, formerly known as Twitter, by British users on the issues of Covid-19 and Brexit, in 2020–2021. Through keyword analysis, appraisal analysis, and micro-linguistic analysis, the study effectively explored how political protests take shape online through the use of “blaming” strategies that protesters use to criticize governments and political leaders online.

Apart from experimenting with different research methodologies, protest studies have also examined new forms of data in recent years, namely visual and digital data. Ekoh and George (2021) explored how young people in Nigeria are protesting on social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram, as well as on the streets of Nigeria against Special Anti-Robbery Squared (known as SARS) officials and police brutality. Memes used in political protests have also been analyzed in the context of Hungary (Lukács, 2021), Poland, (Kampka, 2022), and Russia (Shomova, 2022). The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to generate educational content for protests, and for the mobilization of protesters has also been explored in Kenya against the Finance Bill 2024 (Maina, 2025).

While going through the national and international literature of protest studies, a research gap was identified regarding the methods of analysis used in the Pakistani research landscape. The researchers observed that Pakistani protest studies mainly focus on CDA through analysis of placards, slogans, speeches, and interviews, but lack the incorporation of digital content. As a result, the present study employed a holistic language analysis of protests through the Digital Linguistic Landscape (DLL) framework, which collects and analyzes data not just in textual form like CDA, but also incorporates digital data as well, ranging from online articles and social media posts to memes and AI-generated content.

Research Methodology

This study employed the qualitative research method under a case study approach to focus on the language used in protests against the canal project on the Indus River in Sindh, Pakistan. To investigate the language techniques and resistance narratives used by Sindhi speakers opposing the Indus River Canal Project, Digital Linguistic Landscape (DLL) was adopted as a research design. The purposive sampling was employed to collect the primary data which were based on the social media posts and images used for protests on digital media. In addition to that, news headlines, social media posts, protest songs, chants, and poetry were also collected for the analysis from online platforms such as Facebook, WhatsApp and online news websites. Furthermore, alternative forms of protest language were also accepted, including political cartoons, graffiti, and AI-generated images.

The data were analyzed using content analysis to understand the protest narratives. Hsieh and Shannon (2005) describe that a research employing qualitative content analysis concentrates on the features of language as a means of communication while paying close attention to the text's content or contextual meaning. In this study, the purpose was to analyze content from protest banners, social media posts, songs, poetry, etc., which strengthens the choice of content analysis approach. Besides this, Tilly's (2004) WUNC framework, which stands for Worthiness, Unity, Numbers and Commitment was applied to understand the social movement behind the Indus River Canal Project. In addition, linguistic frames such as lexical choices, syntactic structures, and discourse strategies were also studied in protest texts. To ensure a commitment to ethical research, the social media user IDs are kept confidential, and only the snapshots of the posts are considered for the analysis. For transcription of Sindhi script, the transcription notes have been adopted (Abrar, 2024).

Data Analysis

The data is analyzed to understand the social movements based on the WUNC framework proposed by Tilly (2004). Moreover, and the protest language is analyzed using content analysis with Digital Linguistic Landscape (DLL) approach, both textual and visual elements from social media posts were taken using purposive sampling in qualitative

analysis methods. The goal was to examine how language and semiotic elements in digital spaces (social media platforms) construct protest narratives.

WUNC framework

Worthiness: As explained by Tilly (2004), Worthiness refers to the affirmation and participation of

authoritative bodies like professionals, celebrities, and respectable citizens. The authorization of credible bodies strengthens the message of protestors because they are considered credible citizens and influence a large number of civilians.

Figure 1. Social Media Post

Figure 2. Student Representatives in Protest

As mentioned in Figure. 1, people from all professions and dignitaries, including students from different colleges and universities participated in the protests (see figure 2). Furthermore, participation based on gender was also observed, such as women, (see figure 3), and even transgender individuals, as mentioned in

Figure 1, participated in the protest. Other than that, professionals such as lawyers, as shown in Figure 4, were in the majority. Besides them, doctors also participated equally in the protest, as mentioned in the news headlines shown in Figure 5.

Figure 3. Women Representatives in Protest

Figure 4. Protest by Lawyers

Not only them, but artists and singers also contributed equally by writing poetry and performing songs to advocate their rights (see figure. 6). Khowaja (2025) stated in a newspaper column that Dr. Ishaq Samejo's Ode to Sindh, sung by the legendary singer Sanam Marvi, has become an anthem for protestors. It is a powerful expression appealing for the protection of

the Indus River. This song was played in rallies, and sometimes in school assemblies as well. Protest increases in validity, visibility, and influence when it is supported and disseminated by authorities from a range of professions and through a variety of media platforms.

Figure 5. Protest by Doctors

Figure 6. Protest by Singers

Unity: Tilly's (2004) WUNC framework states that unity is the common identity and purpose displayed by members of a social movement which is an essential element of collective action. Kennedy (2022) explains that solidarity is frequently demonstrated by coordinated acts like marching, chanting, singing, or wearing identical clothing. The demonstration against canal developments on the Indus River is a clear example of this idea.

Throughout these demonstrations, the element of community was evident in a variety of ways. By wearing Ajrak, a traditional Sindhi textile that symbolizes cultural pride and group identity, protesters showed symbolic solidarity (see figure. 7). A collective sense of purpose and belonging was visually reinforced by wearing traditional Topi and Ajrak. To show a united front across political divides in support of the Indus River, participants also brought flags representing different Sindhi political groups (see figure. 8).

Figure 7. Protestors wear Topi & Ajrak

Figure 8. Protestors raise flags in Solidarity

Additionally, Hashtags like #NoMoreCanalsOnIndus, #SaveIndus, and others were intentionally employed on online platforms to stimulate social media algorithms and rally support. By enabling geographically scattered supporters to take part and spread the word, these digital manifestations of solidarity increased the movement's cohesiveness and reach.

Furthermore, the pronoun "we" was frequently used in protest slogans and chants, such as "We reject canals on the Indus" and "Whether you abduct or kill, we will cry and mourn, but we still reject canals on the Indus River" to highlight a collective voice. This rhetorical technique emphasized the community's unified opposition and collective action, validating Tilly's contention that unity is not just symbolic, but

also a strategic and emotional foundation of protest movements.

Numbers: One of the most notable components of Tilly's (2004) WUNC framework is Numbers, which refers to the visible number of individuals actively participating in a collective action. Numbers are critical for determining the size and seriousness of a movement, as they often indicate widespread popular support and increase political leverage. In the case of the protests against the Indus Canal project in Sindh, this feature was prominently represented in the way media headlines and stories continuously emphasized the large number of demonstrators.

News headlines regularly emphasized the scale of popular engagement by using language like 'Sindhu darya bachaRan laaye Sindh je muxtalif ilaqan mein ehtijaaj (massive protests erupt in multiple cities to save Indus river)' as shown in figure. 9, and 'Sindh bhar me ehtijaaj, awam saRkon par nikal aayi (large crowds rally to save the Indus)' as depicted in figure. 10. These headlines not only informed, but also legitimized the movement by demonstrating its widespread support. The repeated use of such numerical emphasis across numerous media platforms increased the protest movement's exposure and perceived legitimacy.

Figure 9. News Headline 1

Figure 10. News Headline 2

Furthermore, the protests were not limited to a particular city or demography; they took place across numerous parts of Sindh, including Hyderabad, Larkana, Sukkur, and Khairpur, exhibiting geographical breadth as well as sheer population. This regional spread demonstrated the extent of public concern and gave the notion that the problem was not isolated but pervasive throughout Sindhi society.

Lastly, public participation also extended to the digital arena, as online platforms gained steam by widely sharing, reposting, and uploading protest pictures, slogans, and hashtags. These digital connections boosted the "numbers" component by bringing together thousands of people who may not have been physically present but actively supported the cause online, thereby expanding its reach.

Commitment: In the WUNC framework, commitment refers to long-term guarantee to support

the cause. One of the most potent demonstrations of commitment was the 27-day long march, during which demonstrators walked from Sukkur to Karachi for almost a month. Figure. 11 highlights the news acknowledging the protestors' long walk from Sukkur to Karachi. Throughout the trek, they stood still for the cause. This prolonged effort not only showed perseverance but also acted as a symbolic journey that united communities and increased the importance of the issue over time. To raise awareness of the perceived injustice, university students also organized hunger strikes (see figure. 12), voluntarily forgoing their comfort and well-being in the process. Such physical hardship and self-denial demonstrated a profound, personal commitment to the movement that went beyond token gestures, demonstrating a level of engagement that is consistent with Tilly's concept of commitment.

Figure 11. News report of Long March

Figure 12. Social Media Post

Figure 13. Hunger Strike

A common protest chant in Sindhi, ‘khanbyo maaryo cha bi kayo, poe bi Sindhu ty dhaRo naa manzuur’ (Whether you abduct or kill, we will cry and mourn, but we still reject canals on the Indus River)’ see figure. 12, which further reflected this attitude of perseverance. This chant demonstrates the intensity of dedication on an emotional and psychological level. The protests against the Indus canal project throughout Sindh can be effectively analyzed via the lens of Tilly's (2004) WUNC paradigm. The movement displayed significant strength in all of these aspects. The participation of renowned public personalities, such as scholars and artists, proved worthiness, while unity was demonstrated through the symbolic use of Ajrak, shared slogans, political flags, and digital solidarity via hashtags. Large-scale public protests, regional mobilization, and widespread online engagement proved numbers, whereas prolonged acts such as the 27-day march and student hunger strikes demonstrated commitment.

Content Analysis

This study employed content analysis to examine the language used in visual and textual media disseminated during the anti-canal protests against the Indus River Canal project in Sindh. The study revealed how language, both written and visual, was used for resistance, influencing public opinion, and proclaiming local identity through a methodical examination of protest imagery. The data set consisted of posters, social media posts, and AI-generated images that showcase a variety of communication strategies, including religious appeals, satirical humor, emotionally charged slogans, and predictive visual narratives alerting people to environmental degradation. These components acted as tactics in addition to informing and persuading. By connecting current complaints to historical concerns of water rights and regional autonomy, historical references served to further solidify the protest's validity. On the examination of these modes of expression, the study

drew attention to the interactions among resistance, cultural discourse, and digital activism in a setting where language served as a protest tool.

One of the most significant slogans was “No more canals on Indus”, which was also used as a hashtag on digital media during the protest. In essence, this slogan is more than just an opposition declaration; it is a language and digital strategy for expressing autonomy, safeguarding resources, and denying marginalization in the context of progress. When a photo of the King Priest of Mohen-jo-Daro waving a banner with this statement was posted (as shown in figure.14), then the voice of protestors became increasingly prominent. Another noteworthy AI-generated graphic depicts a dolphin, a rare species of the Indus River, protesting the need to save the river

or risk extinction, as shown in figure 15. Furthermore, people created an AI image to depict a future image of Punjab being greener and Sindh becoming dryer in order to estimate the potential result of this decision, (see figure. 16). In addition to implying a sense of ownership and emotional commitment to the cause, a picture of their personalized automobile with the same slogan was also shared to show community-wide resistance to canal building, extending it beyond organized protesters (see figure. 17). This particular form of expression enhances an additional symbolic landscape of protest. Similar other slogans were ‘Save the Indus’ and ‘Sindhu ty DhaRo na manzuur (We reject Canals on the Indus)’ which were also used as chants in most of the protest rallies.

Figure 14. AI-generated Image of King Priest

Figure 15. AI-generated Image of Dolphin

In addition, religious figures made a significant contribution to public debate and emotional solidarity around the Indus Canal project. During sermons and assemblies such as in Friday sermons and Eid prayers, religious leaders were instrumental in bringing attention to the cause by presenting it as a

moral and spiritual issue that was connected to the welfare of the whole, rather than merely a political or economic one (see figure. 18). It was even noted that some of the people offered their Eid prayers by the banks of the Indus River to endorse their protest.

Figure 16. AI-generated Image Predicting Future

Figure 17. Slogans on Vehicles

As shown in figure. 19, the social media post from a religious representative said ‘Sindhu tey dhaRo sirf ghair qanuuni na balkay ghair sharae bi aahe (Dams on the Indus are not only illegal but also un-Islamic.)’ see figure. 19. This religious cohesion, which was promoted by spiritual leaders' constant message,

strengthened public support for the project's cause by fostering a sense of urgency and hope. The information demonstrates how religious platforms were effective venues for community integration and advocacy.

It is an unprecedented eid in Sindh. Throughout Sindh Eid day was celebrated as "No New Canals on Indus" day. Prayer leaders condemned new canals project during eid surmon. After eid prayer, people chanted slogans against new canals on Indus. Protest rallies were taken out by women and men in towns and villages of the province. Some people offered eid prayer on boats near dry stream of Indus to mark their protest on eid.

Figure 18. Protest during religious sermons

Figure 19. Protest by religious figures

The data analysis makes strong connections with historical occurrences as well, especially the tragedy of the Battle of Karbala. The fatal ending in Karbala was influenced by the protracted suffering and denial of basic necessities, such as water, in addition to the physical brutality. The similar situation was

emphasized with the historical relevance attached to the Indus Canal Project (see figure. 20). By highlighting the critical role that water plays as a source of life, the metaphor increased the public's sense of urgency in the canal issue.

Figure 20. Historical Reference to the Battle of Karabala

Figure 21. Historical Reference to the Destruction of Nation without Water

In another instance, it was frequently emphasized that areas which had previously experienced water scarcity eventually destroyed and disappeared from the world map (see figure. 21). This historical realization served as a warning to emphasize Sindh's vulnerability in the event that a sustainable water supply is not provided. The data showed the eminent concern of people over Sindh suffering a similar fate in social, agricultural,

and economic collapse that would ultimately result in displacement and a loss of national significance, if projects like the Indus Canal are implemented today. Considering Sindh's environmental conditions, which have already reduced the probability of rainfall, a National Drought Emergency was also declared (see figure. 22).

Figure 22. National Drought Emergency

Figure 23. Humorous Post on Social Media

Figure 24. Sentimental Attachment with the Motherland

While the seriousness of the Indus Canal Project has prompted broader concerns, the data showed a parallel trend of humorous criticism on social media as well, reflecting public dissatisfaction through satire. Several articles and social media posts (see figure. 23) criticized the government's strategy, implying that the projects are planned to fertilize the unproductive regions of Punjab, like the Cholistan desert, by draining resources, particularly water, from the already fertile region of Sindh. Such remarks, while funny on the surface, contained deeper political and

regional critiques, highlighting perceived inequalities in resource allocation. This use of irony and sarcasm was a strong tool for internet activism, allowing citizens to challenge official narratives and express opposition in a socially engaging manner. In conclusion, the analysis emphasizes the Indus River's considerable emotional, historical, and cultural significance for the people of Sindh, who frequently referred to the Sindhu Darya (Indus River) as a "mother" (see figure. 24) as a critical source of survival, identity, and livelihood. This maternal

symbolism reinforced popular sentiment against any interruption to the natural flow. People continually fought for the river's uninterrupted flow, claiming that halting it could compromise not only agriculture but Sindh's very life.

Discussion and Future Recommendations

The purpose of this study was to investigate two important aspects of the protest movement against the Indus canal project in Sindh: the protestors' linguistic framing techniques and the expression of Tilly's (2004) idea of worthiness, unity, numbers, and commitment (WUNC). According to the findings, demonstrators used strong, culturally relevant language such as oppositional rhetoric, emotive appeals, and shared identity, to frame their resistance. Chants and slogans, frequently in Sindhi, were used to resist authority and to strengthen group cohesion. As argumentative tools, inclusive pronouns served to bring opposing voices together in support of a common goal.

The analysis using Tilly's WUNC framework also showed that the protest movement had a strong strategic foundation, in addition to being rich in symbolism. Credible individuals like academics and artists participated in project worthiness; unity was demonstrated through coordinated slogans, social media campaigns, and collective dress codes; numbers were visible through the extensive physical and digital mobilization; and commitment was evidently demonstrated through physically demanding actions like a 27-day march and student hunger strikes. Collectively, these factors contributed to maintaining the protest's momentum and establishing its validity in the eyes of the public. As a reflection of the wider limitations of protest movements that mostly rely on performative and affective components without institutional support, it is unclear whether the movement will be successful in changing policy or stopping the canal project.

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be made for future research. For instance, analyzing the Indus canal demonstrations in comparison to other South Asian environmental or water rights campaigns may provide important information about the political outcomes, language tactics, and protest cultures of the region. Moreover, for future mobilizations to represent the

entire range of stakeholders impacted by such projects, greater inclusion across gender, class, and age groups should be guaranteed. This would reinforce the "numbers" and "worthiness" aspects of WUNC.

REFERENCES

- Abrar, A. (2024). Sociolinguistic analysis of naming practices: A comparative study of English and local personal names. M.Phil. Thesis. Department of English, University of Karachi.
- Akhtar, A., Aziz, S., & Almas, N. (2021). The poetics of Pakistani patriarchy: A critical Analysis of the protest signs in women's march Pakistan 2019. *Journal of Feminist Scholarship*, 18(18), 136-153.
- Catanzaro, M., & Collin, P. (2023). Kids communicating climate change: learning from the visual language of the SchoolStrike4Climate protests. *Educational Review*, 75(1), 9-32.
- DAWN. (2025, February 16). Ambitious project launched to turn Cholistan green. DAWN.COM. <https://www.dawn.com/news/1892222>
- Ekoh, P. C., & George, E. O. (2021). The role of digital technology in the EndSars protest in Nigeria during COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of human rights and social work*, 6(2), 161-162.
- Hansson, S., Page, R., & Fuoli, M. (2022). Discursive strategies of blaming: The language of judgment and political protest online. *Social Media+ Society*, 8(4), 20563051221138753.
- Hsieh, H.-F., & Shannon, S. E. (2005). Three Approaches to Qualitative Content Analysis. *Qualitative Health Research*, 15(9), 1277-1288. doi:10.1177/1049732305276687
- Iyoha, O. (2023). Critical discourse analysis and the study of protest and conflict representation in the print media: A Review.
- Kaleem, N., Siraj, S. M. S., & Asif, M. (2022). Critical discourse analysis of political slogans of major Pakistani political parties in election. *Pakistan Journal of International Affairs*, 5(3), 16-25.

- Kampka, A. (2022). Banners and Memes: The rhetoric of protests in defense of democracy and women's rights in Poland in 2015 and 2020. *Performance Research*, 27(3-4), 125-135.
- Khowaja, K. K. (2025, May 15). Sanam Marvi's 'Sindhu Wahando Rahando' has become an anthem for Sindhis protesting against the canal project. Images. <https://images.dawn.com/news/1193558/sanam-marvis-sindhu-wahando-rahando-has-become-an-anthem-for-sindhis-protesting-against-the-canal-project>
- Kennedy, C.-R. (2022). Worthiness, unity, numbers and commitment: Strengthening qualitative corpus methods in the critical discourse analysis of protest press coverage. *Discourse & Society*, 33(5), 611-630.
- Lukács, G. (2021). Internet memes as protest media in populist Hungary. *Visual anthropology review*, 37(1), 52-76.
- Maina, T. M. (2025). Artificial Intelligence in Digital Activism: Catalysing Kenya's Protest to the Finance Bill 2024. *Int. J. Sci. Res. in Multidisciplinary Studies* Vol, 11(1).
- Ming, L., & Wang, G. (2022). An introduction to the special issue on "Language, Politics and Media: The Hong Kong protests". *Journal of Language and Politics*, 21(1), 1-16.
- Nazar, Y. (2025, March 9). Political crisis in Sindh and the Cholistan project. *The Friday Times*. <https://thefridaytimes.com/08-Mar-2025/political-crisis-in-sindh-and-the-cholistan-project>
- Nawaz, M. H., Riaz, U., Parveen, A., & Nasia, A. (2024). Constructing national identity: A critical discourse analysis of Pakistani political campaign slogans. *Futurity Proceedings*, 1.
- Qureshi, R., Baig, M. B., & Belgacem, A. O. (2024). Climate change and innovative ecological interventions through climate-smart agriculture in the Cholistan desert of Pakistan. In *Climate-Smart and Resilient Food Systems and Security* (pp. 215-257). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Shomova, S. (2022). "Hieroglyphs of protest": Internet memes and the protest movement in Russia. *Problems of Post-Communism*, 69(3), 232-241.
- Siddiqua, A., Gong, J., & Aksar, I. A. (2023). Twitter trolling of Pakistani female journalists: A patriarchal society glance. *Media, Culture & Society*, 45(6), 1303-1314.
- Tilly, C. (2004). *Social Movements, 1768-2004*, Paradigm Press.
- Van Dijk, T. (1998). *Opinions and ideologies in the press. Approaches to media discourse*. Eds. A. Bell and P. Garret Malden. M.A.: Blackwell.
- Van Dijk TA (2015) *Critical discourse analysis*. In: Tannen D, Hamilton HE, Schiffrin D (eds) *The Handbook of Discourse Analysis*. Chichester: Wiley Blackwell, pp.466-485.
- Waqar, H., & Khan, S. A. (2025). Analyzing power dynamics in Pakistani political discourse: A CDA-based study. *Qlantic Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 6(1), 38-50..

